

Fold deformation of the Fatricum – a case study from the Banka section (Považský Inovec Mts., Slovakia)

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Abstract: Unique temporal exposure of Fatricum Zliechov sub-unit in the road cut near Banka (Piešťany district, Slovakia) allowed to document deformed sedimentary sequence ranging from Rhaetian to Albian. It was possible to identify the Fatra, Kapienec, Osnica and Párnica formations. Due to their lithology and better exposure, the latter two were characterized by a variety of fold and fault structures. Their strong deformation results in significant thickness reduction of several members of the sequence and suggests that most of sedimentary contacts are tectonized. West-vergent folds and reverse faults are classified to the Palealpine (Mid- to Late Cretaceous) deformation phase related to the thin-skinned emplacement of Fatric nappes. The east-vergent low-angle thrust faults and folds represent younger retro-vergent (probably Oligocene–Early Miocene) “back-thrusting” phase. Younger normal faults are a result of Miocene to Quaternary extensional events.

Key words: kinematics, thin-skinned tectonics, folding, back-thrusting, Fatricum, Zliechov sub-unit

Introduction

The Miocene horst block of the Považský Inovec Mts. (PI) is situated in the western part of the Western Carpathians (Slovakia) and surrounded by the embayments of the Pannonian Basin Miocene sediments (Fig. 1; Ivanička et al., 2007, 2011; Hók et al., 2016). Thanks to its characteristic horst and basin structure, this zone in the northern Internal Western Carpathians (*sensu* Vass et al., 1988 or Hók et al., 2014) is called the Core mountains belt. Each of Core mountains is built by subautochthonous Tatricum, as well as Fatric and Hronic cover nappes. The Fatricum (term defined by Andrusov et al., 1973, cf. Plašienka et al., 1997a, 1997b), or formerly known as the Križna nappe (Andrusov, 1935, 1938; Maheľ, 1983, 1986) represents originally 1–2 km thin, more or less imbricated thrust system (tectonic slices, duplexes and recumbent folds; Kováč,

2007), generally composed of Triassic to Early Cretaceous carbonates and minor siliciclastics. Internal structure is usually divided by lithofacial criteria into one or two lower-order thrust sheets, often called “partial nappes” (Maheľ, 1983; Plašienka et al., 1997b; Bezák et al., 2004). Structurally lower and spatially less abundant is the so-called Vysoká (Belá and Beckov) sub-unit, with shallow water Jurassic formations. The more widely distributed Zliechov sub-unit is forming structurally higher thrust-sheet characterized by the deep water Jurassic deposits. Deformation and emplacement of the Fatricum was studied by numerous authors from its root regions in the Veporic Veľký bok unit, through the regions where its nappe position is apparent (Jaroš, 1971; Plašienka, 1983, 1995, 2003; Prokešová, 1994; Plašienka & Prokešová, 1996; Kováč, 2007; Pečeňa & Vojtko, 2011; Sentpetery & Hók, 2012; Prokešová et al., 2012). The Fatricum is generally

Fig. 1. Location of investigated territory. **a** – Location of the Považský Inovec Mts. in the Western Carpathians. **b** – Tectonic map of the Považský Inovec Mts. (modified from Bezák et al., 2011). 1 – Tatric crystalline basement, 2 – Tatric Upper Paleozoic volcanosedimentary Kálnica Group, 3 – Tatric Mesozoic rocks, 4 – Fatricum, 5 – Hronicum, 6 – Upper Cretaceous Horné Belice Group, 7 – Cenozoic sediments. **c** – Geological map of the area between Ratnovce and Moravany nad Váhom with marked location of the studied road cut (simplified from Elečko et al., 2008).

characterized by the north- to northwest-vergent Paleozoic structures (Prokešová, 1994; Kováč & Bendík, 2002; Plašienka, 2003). The nappe deformation lasted from the Albian and the emplacement occurred during the Middle Turonian according to earlier assumptions (Plašienka, 1997; Plašienka, 1999; Prokešová et al., 2012). However, also younger - Middle Turonian–Santonian sediments are documented from below the sole of the Fatricum in the Považský Inovec Mts in the Striebornica section (Pelech et al., 2017). It suggests that the emplacement occurred after the Santonian, thus later than in the other Core mountains.

Fatricum rock sequences are known mostly from the central and western portion of the Považský Inovec Mts. (Ivanička et al., 2007; Ivanička et al., 2011). The Zliechov sub-unit is dominant in central block of the PI. The occurrences in the northern block are limited to the margins of the PI near Beckov and Patrovec, where they are formed by the Vysoká Unit (term Beckov Unit is used in PI; Pelech et al., 2012).

This paper presents observations of the Fatricum deformation from the Banka section in the Považský Inovec Mts. and compares it with situation in nearby Moravany nad Váhom.

Aims and methods

Main aim of this paper is to study structural characteristics, lithology and age of the sequence in the distinctive exposure of the Mesozoic carbonate rocks observed during the years 2013–2014 in temporary uncovered road cut south of the Banka village (Piešťany district, Western Slovakia). Additional structural data from the Fatricum nappe of central and northern Považský Inovec Mts. are further discussed. Due to the need of verification of the stratigraphic assignment of the studied rocks, 16 samples were collected for the preparation of thin-sections, and 2 samples were collected for washing. The samples of marls were washed through sieves with 71µm and 125µm mesh size. Calpionellids and their stratigraphic age was determined according to Reháková & Michalík (1997).

Results Stratigraphy

Approximately 180 m long section (Fig. 2) was temporarily exposed in artificial cut during earthworks on the new road south of the Banka village (N48.569821°,

Fig. 2. Mesoscopic structures and lithology in the road cut near Banka (N48.569821°, E17.842179°).

E17.842179°). Studied section is oriented in WNW–ESE direction and exposes approx. 80 m thick (true thickness) sequence consisting of various lithostratigraphic members of the Fatric Zliechov sub-unit.

The oldest rocks assigned to the Rhaetian Fatra Formation (cf. Gaździcki et al., 1979; Tomašových, 2004) are present in the SE part of the section (168–180 m) and separated from the higher members by a normal fault. Grey limestones are characterized by the packed biomicrite to biosparite (packstone, grainstone to floatstone) with fragments of bivalves, gastropods, bryozoans and brachiopod shells, locally also micrite (calcimudstone) is present, samples 0 and 13, Fig. 3a, b).

Overlying sediments occurring south-east of the normal fault (150–168 m) are represented by the grey and reddish sandy limestones and grey shales. Limestones are characterized as a packed oolitic biomicrite to biosparite with hematite cement (oolitic grainstone). It contains chamosite ooids, clastic quartz of fine sand fraction and remains of bivalves, brachiopods and echinoderm fragments (sample 12, Fig. 3c, d). It probably represents Lower Jurassic Kopianec Formation (cf. Gaździcki et al., 1979). Other Middle and Late Jurassic formations are missing in this part of the section.

The higher portion of the sedimentary sequence (20–117 m) exposed to the north-west of the young normal fault consists of strongly deformed (folded and faulted) pelagic carbonates, represented by the pink and grey micritic limestones that probably belong to the Osnica Formation (Michalík et al., 1990 and 1993). The formation is characterized as altered biomicrite (mudstone to wackestone). Alteration is manifested by recrystallization of finer grained material of matrix, obliteration of finer bioclasts and higher abundance of authigenic pyrite, in the microscale and partly by the occurrence of pink and reddish weathering of the rocks and veins, filled by opaque minerals in the macroscale. Limestones contain occasional calpionellids *Calpionella elliptica* Cadisch and (from sample 17, Fig. 3d), *Remaniella duranddelgai* Pop (Fig. 3g), *Calpionellites oblonga* (Cadisch) (from sample 5) and *Calpionellites major* (Colom) (sample 6, Fig. 3f) indicating Middle Berriasian to Early Valanginian age.

Overlying grey clayey shales and grey limestones (117–132 m) are separated by faults. Limestones are partly recrystallized mudstones containing planktonic foraminifers *Globigerinelloides algerianus* Cushman & TenDam, which allow to biostratigraphically date the observed sediments into the Late Aptian *Globigerinelloides algerianus* Zone. Abundant sections of *Globigerinelloides ferreolensis* Moullade, *Hedbergella aptiana* Glaessner, *Hedbergella infracretacea* Glaessner were present (sample P1). In the sample above yielding only small globular chambered planktonic foraminifers, rare *Spiroplectinata annectens* (Parker & Jones) (Fig. 3i, sample 10) was present in the as-

semblage, suggesting a ?Late Aptian but mostly an Albian age (Tyszka & Thies, 2001). Based on the observed lithology, position in sedimentary sequence and stratigraphic age, the grey clayey shales and limestones are assigned to the Párnica Formation (cf. Hauer, 1872; Boorová & Filo, 2013).

Observed thickness of the Fatra, Kopianec and Párnica formations is significantly reduced due to strong deformation. Missing parts of sedimentary sequence, e.g. Jurassic spotted limestones of the Janovky Formation or radiolarites, are the result of repeated tectonic reduction during nappe emplacement, as well as later tectonic events. The older Triassic members are missing, as the studied section represents the sequence preserved above the Carpathian Keuper décollement (Prokešová et al., 2012).

The Mesozoic formations are covered by Quaternary sediments. They represent yellowish-grey silty loess of Würmian age (Ivanička et al., 2011). Overlying deposits are represented by deluvial loams and coarse-grained debris of pebble to cobble size. They are post-Würmian to Holocene age.

Structural geology

As it was stated before, the sedimentary sequence is strongly folded and faulted. Expressive fold deformation was followed by later faulting. Folding caused redistribution of the bedding planes into two groups with east and west oriented dip (Fig. 4a). The fold deformation was a result of flexural slip that is common in the well bedded sedimentary bodies. It is locally characterized by the striae and slickensides on the bedding planes. Overall 39 fold axes were recorded. Asymmetric mesoscale folds with dip of the axial plane to the east and dominant foreland-vergent tectonic transport (top to west or northwest) are prevailing (Fig. 5a–c). Good examples are seen in the segments between 55–75, 87–100 and 132–137 m (Fig. 2). The fold axes are generally trending N–S, with local undulations (Fig. 4b). Another west-vergent structure is represented by the thrust sheet of Párnica Formation located in the pink micritic limestones between 118–132 m. The shales and claystones of the Párnica Formation display prominent east-dipping cleavage which highlights the dominant direction of tectonic transport (Fig. 5b, d).

Complex overturned fold (“digitation”) present between 55–65 m is similar to larger-order structures known from the Morcles nappe of the Western Alps, where it is interpreted as a result of simple shear deformation during later evolution of the nappe body (Ramsay et al., 1983). The same explanation could be applied to the observed structure in the road cut.

Fold axes perpendicular to dominant WNW-vergent folds, otherwise relatively common in the Považský

Fig. 3. **a** – Biosparite consisting of densely packed bivalvia fragments. Sample 13. Rhaetian Fatra Formation. **b** – Wackestone to floatstone with a gastropod shell, Sample 0. Rhaetian Fatra Formation. **c** – Sandy-crinoidal limestone, plane polarized light (left), crossed polarized light (right), Kopianec Formation. Sample 12. **d** – Sandy crinoidal limestone with chamositic Fe-oids, plane polarized light (left), crossed polarized light (right), Kopianec Formation. Sample 12. **e** – *Calpionella elliptica* Cadisch (Sample 17). **f** – *Calpionellites major* (Colom, Sample 6). **g** – *Remaniella duranddelgai* Pop (Sample 5). **h** – Section of “hedbergellid” planktonic foraminifer (Sample 10). **i** – Section of *Spiroplectinata annectens* (Parker & Jones, Sample 10).

Fig. 4. Structural measurements in the Fatric sequence at the studied road cut near Banka. **a** - Orientation of bedding planes. **b** - Orientation of fold axes (+).

Inovec Mts. (cf. Plašienka & Marko, 1993; Pelech et al., 2016; Pelech & Hók, 2017) were present only in negligible extent.

The investigated Fatricum succession is, in addition to ordinary folds with the west-vergence, also deformed by back-thrusts and folds with east-vergence. The latter are less numerous than the west-vergent folds but more striking. They are mostly represented by passive, flexural folds which bend the original north-vergent and neutral folds (Fig. 2 - 36–38 m). However, some seemingly east-vergent folds are in fact only Z-folds of larger complex folds (Fig. 6b). Locally observed S-C' bands also indicate tectonic transport to the east. Back-thrusts modify the original structure and rarely separate rigid blocks with structural paragenesis of the northwestern vergence (Fig. 6a). Back-thrust structure between 75–80 m (possibly continuing up to 103 m) represents evidently a younger (thus “post-nappe”) superimposed deformation phase. According to regional context, we can assume that the back-thrusting has occurred after the Santonian and before Middle Miocene.

Apart of the ductile structures several younger normal faults were observed in the road cut as well. It is worth mentioning that some of them apparently offset the Quaternary sediments (Fig. 6c).

Moravany nad Váhom

The second section in the Fatricum is documented in a road cut in the valley of Hraničný kanál Brook, west of the Moravany nad Váhom (48.587167° N, 17.867667° E). Grey and black calcareous shales and sandy limestones of the Kapienec Formation represent part of the Zliechov sub-unit. The observed sequence is generally monoclinal dipping to the west and southwest (Fig. 7a). The axial plane cleavage is dipping to the southeast, and the fold axes are oriented in southwest-northeast direction (Fig. 7b,

6d). Aforementioned indicators suggest top to northwest tectonic transport of the Fatricum at this locality.

Discussion

Tectonic transport direction of North Veporic Veľký bok Unit between Poniky and Liptovská Teplička (Plašienka, 1983, 1995) is top to NW-NNW, that is similar to supposed internal portions of the Fatricum in the northeastern (Rázdiel) part of the Tribeč Mts. (Hók et al., 1994). In the Sklené Teplice area, the sense of tectonic transport of the Northern Veporic sedimentary cover was to the west (Hók et al., 2013). In the area between Banská Bystrica, Korytnica and Ružomberok, the direction of the tectonic transport of the Fatricum was to the NW and NNW (Prokešová, 1994). Direction of the tectonic transport in the area of Donovaly was identified as top to NW (Kováč & Bendík, 2002). Observations from the northern slopes of the Nízke Tatry Mts. show top to NNW or N tectonic transport of the Fatricum (Plašienka, 2003). Tectonic transport of Belá sub-unit (equivalent of Vysoká sub-unit) in the Strážovské vrchy Mts. is to the WNW, while the Zliechov sub-unit was thrust to the NNW in this region (Pečeňa & Vojtko, 2011). Documented sense of tectonic transport of the Beckov sub-unit near Patrovec in the northeastern Považský Inovec Mts. is top to NNW (Pelech et al., 2012). Overall picture is summarized in Fig. 8.

While the recorded tectonic transport of Northern Veporicum and Fatricum is relatively uniform east of Banská Bystrica (Central Slovak Fault System *sensu* Kováč & Hók, 1993), thus top to NNW. More to the west, the deviations from the NNW direction of tectonic transport are more common. Diverse directions of movement are recorded as well in the Považský Inovec Mts. While the direction of the Beckov (Vysoká) sub-unit emplacement in the northern part of the mountain range (Patrovec) is to the NNW (Pelech et al., 2012), the directions of the Zliechov

Fig. 5. a – Folded part of road cut section with low angle fault (?back-thrust; 85–100 m); b – Duplex in shales and organodetrritic limestones of the Párnica Formation (road cut section between 117–130 m); c – Foreland-vergent inclined fold in limestones of the Osnica Fm. (54–55 m). d – Detail view on cleavage in the marly shales of the Párnica Fm. (from figure 5 b).

Fig. 6. **a** – Older foreland-vergent reverse fault above younger back-thrust with south-east vergence (75–80 m) in limestones of the Osnica Formation. **b** – Fold with apparent vergence to the hinterland, in fact representing parasitic – lower order Z-fold in the overturned limb of “digitation” (61–63 m). **c** – Quaternary normal fault offsetting folded Mesozoic sequence as well as Quaternary debris. **d** – North-west-vergent fold and axial plane cleavage in the sandy limestones of the Kapienec Formation near Moravany nad Váhom.

Fig. 7. Structural characteristics of the studied rocks at the locality near Moravany nad Váhom. **a** – Bedding planes. **b** – Cleavage (grey) and fold-axes (x).

sub-unit in the central part of the mountain range vary between NW (Moravany nad Váhom) and W (Banka). This difference suggests that structural discordance might exist between the Vysoká and Zliechov sub-units (“partial nappes”). Kováč (2007) explains similar phenomenon in the various thrust sheets of Fatricum in Demänová and Iľanovo valleys as a result of the existence of oblique thrust ramps. In PI, it can be alternatively a result of dextral movement on the Hrádok-Zlatníky shear zone (Pelech & Hók, 2017). Prevailing west (Fig. 4b) or northwest direction of tectonic transport, well manifested at the studied road cut near Banka, can be considered as a consequence of the Cenozoic counter-clockwise block rotation known from western segment of the Western Carpathians (Márton et al., 2013; Márton et al., 2015).

The studied road cut exhibits also several east-vergent structures. Similar structures with hinterland (generally south- or southeast) vergence are known from Northern Veporicum-Fatricum system. In the Northern Veporic area, they are usually interpreted as related to the final phase of convergence of the root area of the nappe (Plašienka, 1983, p. 224). Retro-vergent structures can form contemporary to the foreland-vergent thrusts (e.g. McClay & Whitehouse, 2004). However, the back-thrusts in the area of the Považský Inovec Mts. are not a result of such processes. Regional context suggests that they represent younger superimposed retro-vergent deformation that is observed along the entire western edge of the Western Car-

pathians (Marko et al., 2005; Pešková, 2011; Hók et al., 2016). They are usually interpreted as Oligocene–Early Miocene in age (Hók et al., 2016).

Conclusions

This contribution presents result of the structural analysis of the Fatric sequences in central part of the Považský Inovec Mts. It documents structural style and thin-skinned tectonics of the Fatric cover nappe in the well exposed road cut near the Banka village. The main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The sedimentary sequence composed of the Fatra, Kopienec, Osnica and Párnica formations ranging from Rhetian to Albian is tectonically reduced and strongly deformed. In majority the “sedimentary” contacts are tectonized. This knowledge can have important implications for other areas as the Zliechov sub-unit represents one of the most common Mesozoic sequences, occurring at the surface in many regions of the Core mountains in Slovakia.
- 2) Forward-vergent thrusts and steep reverse faults together with west- and northwest-vergent folds of different shape and magnitude represent the main Paleozoic structures of probably Early to Late Cretaceous age.
- 3) Back-thrusts of supposed Oligocene to Early Miocene age are documented. They are characterized by the ret-

Fig. 8. Simplified tectonic map of Slovakia (modified from Biely et al., 1996) with marked sense of tectonic transport of the Fatricum (grey arrows) and Northern Veporicum nappes (white arrow) during Paleozoic phase. Tectonic transport directions from Plašienka (1983, 2003), Hók et al. (1994, 2013), Prokešová (1994), Kováč & Bendík (2002) and Pečeňa & Vojtko (2011) and own data.

ro-vergent top to the east tectonic transport and superimposed on older foreland-vergent structures.

- 4) Cenozoic normal faults including several Quaternary faults represent the youngest deformation phase.

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References

- ANDRUSOV, D., 1935: Subtatranské príkrovy Západných Karpát. *Carpatica, Ř. B (Praha), 1, 50.*
- ANDRUSOV, D., 1938: Geologie Slovenska. Sbor pro výzkum Slovenska a Podkarpatské Rusi. *Praha, Orbis, 111 p.*
- ANDRUSOV, D., BYSTRICKÝ, J. & FUSÁN, O., 1973: Outline of the structure of the Western Carpathians. Guide book, X Congress CBGA. *Bratislava, Geol. Úst. D. Štúra, 44 p.*
- BEZÁK, V., BROSKA, I., ELEČKO, M., HAVRILA, M., IVANIČKA, J., JANOČKO, J., KALIČIAK, M., KONEČNÝ, V., LEXA, J., MELLO, J., PLAŠIENKA, D., POLÁK, D., POTFAJ, M. & VASS, D., 2004: Tectonic map of Slovak Republic. *Bratislava, Št. Geol. Úst. D. Štúra.*
- BEZÁK, V., BIELY, A., ELEČKO, M., KONEČNÝ, V., MELLO, J., POLÁK, M. & POTFAJ, M., 2011: A new synthesis of the geological structure of Slovakia – the general geological map at 1 : 200,000 scale. *Geol. Quart., 55, 1, 1 – 8.*
- BIELY, A., BEZÁK, V., ELEČKO, M., KALIČIAK, M., KONEČNÝ, V., LEXA, J., MELLO, J., NEMČOK, J., POTFAJ, M., RAKÚS, M., VASS, D., VOZÁR, J. & VOZÁROVÁ, A., 1996: Geological map of Slovakia 1 : 500 000. *Bratislava, Geol. Surv. Slovak Republic.*
- BOOROVÁ, D. & FILO, I., 2013: Štúdium párnického súvrstvia na stratotypovom profile Žaškov (križňanský príkrov). *Miner. Slov., 45, 61 – 68.*
- ELEČKO, M. (ed.), POLÁK, M., FORDINÁL, K., BEZÁK, V., IVANIČKA, J., MELLO, J., KONEČNÝ, V., ŠIMON, L., NAGY, A., POTFAJ, M., MAGLAY, J., BROSKA, I., BUČEK, S., GROSS, P., HAVRILA, M., HÓK, J., KOHÚT, M., KOVÁČIK, M., MADARÁS, J., OLŠAVSKÝ, M., PRISTAŠ, J., SALAJ, J. & VOZÁROVÁ, A., 2008: Prehľadná geologická mapa Slovenskej republiky 1 : 200 000. Mapový list 35 – Trnava (General Geological Map of the Slovak Republic 1 : 200 000, Map sheet 35 – Trnava). *Bratislava, Št. Geol. Úst. D. Štúra.*
- GAŽDZICKI, A., MICHALÍK, J. & SÝKORA, M., 1979: An Upper Triassic – Lower Jurassic sequence in the Križna nappe (West Tatra mountains, West Carpathians, Czechoslovakia). *Západ. Karpaty, Sér. Geol., 5, 119 – 148.*
- HAUER, F. R. VON, 1872: Geologische Uebersichtskarte der österreichischen Monarchie. *Jb. K.-Kön. geol. Reichsanst., 22, 149 – 228.*
- HÓK, J., IVANIČKA, J. & KOVÁČIK, M., 1994: Geologická stavba rázdielskej časti Tríbeča – nové poznatky a diskusia. *Miner. Slov., 26, 3, 192 – 196.*
- HÓK, J., PELECH, O. & SLOBODOVÁ, Z., 2013: Kinematická analýza homínových komplexov veporika a hronika v oblasti sklenoteplického ostrova (stredoslovenské neovulkanity). *Acta Geol. Slov., 5, 2, 129 – 134.*
- HÓK, J., ŠUJAN, M. & ŠÍPKA, F., 2014: Tektonické členenie Západných Karpát – prehľad názorov a nový prístup. *Acta Geol. Slov., 6, 2, 135 – 143.*
- HÓK, J., KOVÁČ, M., PELECH, O., PEŠKOVÁ, I., VOJTKO, R. & KRÁLIKOVÁ, S., 2016: The Alpine tectonic evolution of the Danube Basin and its northern periphery (southwestern Slovakia). *Geol. Carpath., 67, 5, 495 – 505.*
- IVANIČKA, J., HAVRILA, M., KOHÚT, M. (eds.), OLŠAVSKÝ, M., HÓK, J., KOVÁČIK, M., MADARÁS, J., POLÁK, M., RAKÚS, M., FILO, I., ELEČKO, M., FORDINÁL, K., MAGLAY, J., PRISTAŠ, J., BUČEK, S., ŠIMON, L., KUBEŠ, P., SCHERER, S. & ZUBEREC, J., 2007: Geologická mapa Považského Inovca a jv. časti Trenčianskej kotliny, M = 1 : 50 000. *Bratislava, Št. Geol. Úst. D. Štúra.*
- IVANIČKA, J., KOHÚT, M. (eds.), OLŠAVSKÝ, M., HAVRILA, M., HÓK, J., KOVÁČIK, M., MADARÁS, J., POLÁK, M., RAKÚS, M., FILO, I., ELEČKO, M., FORDINÁL, K., MAGLAY, J., PRISTAŠ, J., BUČEK, S., ŠIMON, L., KUBEŠ, P., SCHERER, S. & ZUBEREC, J., 2011: Vysvetlivky ku geologickej mape regiónu Považský Inovca a jv. časť Trenčianskej kotliny, M = 1 : 50 000. *Bratislava, Št. Geol. Úst. D. Štúra, 389 p.*
- JAROŠ, J., 1971: Tectonic styles of the homelands of superficial nappes. *Rozpr. Čs. Akad. Věd, Ř. mat. přír. Věd, 81, 6, 59.*
- KOVÁČ, P., 2007: The internal structure of Palealpine thrusts of the Western Carpathians: A case study from the Križna thrust system. *Centr. Eur. Geol., 50, 1, 19 – 28.*
- KOVÁČ, P. & HÓK, J., 1993: The Central Slovak Fault System – The field evidence of a strike slip. *Geol. Carpath., 44, 3, 155 – 159.*
- KOVÁČ, P. & BENDÍK, A., 2002: Štruktúrna analýza adnetských vápencov na lokalite Zvolen – Donovaly. *Miner. Slov., 34, 207 – 210.*
- MAHEJ, M., 1983: Križna nappe, example of polyfacial and polystructural unit. *Miner. Slov., 15, 3, 193 – 216.*
- MAHEJ, M., 1986: Geológia Československých Karpát 1. Palealpinske jednotky. *Bratislava, Veda, Vyd. Slov. Akad. Vied, 510 p.*
- MARKO, F., VOJTKO, R., PLAŠIENKA, D., SLIVA, E., JABLONSKÝ, J., REICHWALDER, P. & STAREK, D., 2005: A contribution to the tectonics of the Periklippen zone near Zázrivá (Western Carpathians). *Slovak Geol. Mag., 11, 1, 37 – 43.*
- MÁRTON, E., GRABOWSKI, J., PLAŠIENKA, D., TÚNYI, I., KROBICKI, M., HAAS, J. & PETHE, M., 2013: New paleomagnetic results from the Upper Cretaceous red marls of the Pieniny Klippen Belt, Western Carpathians: Evidence for general CCW rotation and implications for the origin of the structural arc formation. *Tectonophysics, 592, 1 – 13.*
- MÁRTON, E., GRABOWSKI, J., TOKARSKI, A. K. & TÚNYI, I., 2015: Palaeomagnetic results from the fold and thrust belt of the

- Western Carpathians: An overview. In: Pueyo, E. L., Cifelli, F., Sussman, A. J. & Oliva-Urcia, B. (eds.): Palaeomagnetism in Fold and Thrust Belts: New Perspectives. *Geol. Soc. London, Spec. Publ.*, 425, 7 – 37.
- MCCLAY, K. R. & WHITEHOUSE, P. S., 2004: Analog modeling of doubly vergent thrust wedges. In: *McClay, K. R.* (ed.): *Thrust tectonics and hydrocarbon systems. Amer. Assoc. Petrol. Geol. Mem.*, 82, 184 – 206.
- MICHALÍK, J., VAŠÍČEK, Z. & BORZA, V., 1990: Aptychy, tintinidy a stratigrafia hraničných jursko-kriedových súvrství v profile Strážovce (zliechovská jednotka krížňanského príkrovu, Strážovské vrchy, Centrálné Západné Karpaty). *Knih. Zem. Plyn Nafta*, 9a, 69 – 92.
- MICHALÍK, J., VAŠÍČEK, Z. & BORZA, V., 1993: Biostratigrafia a mikrofacie vrchnojurskej a spodnokriedovej panvovej sekvencie v krížňanskom príkrove fatrika (profil Zrázy pri Dolnej Porube, Strážovské vrchy). *Geol. Práce, Spr.*, 97, 105 – 112.
- PEČEŇA, L. & VOJTKO, R., 2011: Nové poznatky o geologickej stavbe fatrickej jednotky v okolí Valaskej Belej (Strážovské vrchy, Západné Karpaty). *Miner. Slov.*, 43, 19 – 30.
- PELECH, O., SOTÁK, J. & HÓK, J., 2012: Geological setting of the Patrovec block in the Považský Inovec Mts. Western Carpathians. *Miner. Slov.*, 44, 3, 231 – 240.
- PELECH, O., HÓK, J., PEŠKOVÁ, I. & HAVRILA, M., 2016: Structural position of the Upper Cretaceous sediments in the Považský Inovec Mts. (Western Carpathians). *Acta Geol. Slov.*, 8, 1, 43 – 58.
- PELECH, O. & HÓK, J., 2017: Metodika mezoskopického štúdia strižných zón a jej aplikácia pri kinematickej analýze hrádocko-zlatnickej strižnej zóny v Považskom Inovci. *Geol. Práce, Spr.*, 130, 47 – 67.
- PELECH, O., HÓK, J. & JÓZSA, Š., 2017: Turonian-Santonian sediments in the Tatricum of the Považský Inovec Mts. (Internal Western Carpathians, Slovakia). *Austrian J. Earth Sci.*, 110, 1, 19 – 33.
- PEŠKOVÁ, I., 2011: Tektonická interpretácia západného úseku kontaktnej zóny externíd a interníd Západných Karpát. Dissertation thesis. Manuscript. *Bratislava, Archive of Department of geol. and paleont.*, 94 p.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., 1983: Kinematický obraz niektorých štruktúr severného veporika vo vzťahu k formovaniu krížňanského príkrovu. *Miner. Slov.*, 15, 3, 217 – 231.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., 1995: Cleavages and folds in changing tectonic regimes: The Veľký Bok Mesozoic cover unit of the Veporicum (Nízke Tatry Mts., Central Western Carpathians). *Slovak Geol. Mag.*, 2, 97 – 113.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., 1997: Cretaceous tectochronology of the Central Western Carpathians, Slovakia. *Geol. Carpath.*, 48, 2, 99 – 111.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., 1999: Tektochronológia a paleotektonický model jursko-kriedového vývoja centrálnych Západných Karpát. *Bratislava, Veda, Vyd. Slov. Akad. Vied*, 125 p.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., 2003: Development of basement-involved fold and thrust structures exemplified by the Tatric-Fatric-Veporic nappe system of the Western Carpathians (Slovakia). *Geodin. Acta*, 16, 21 – 38.
- PLAŠIENKA, D. & MARKO, F., 1993: Geologická stavba strednej časti Považského Inovca. *Miner. Slov.*, 25, 11 – 25.
- PLAŠIENKA, D. & PROKEŠOVÁ, R., 1996: Towards an evolutionary tectonic model of the Krížna cover nappe (Western Carpathians, Slovakia). *Slovak Geol. Mag.*, 3 – 4, 279 – 286.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., GREČULA, P., PUTIŠ, M., KOVÁČ, M. & HOVORKA, D., 1997a: Evolution and structure of the Western Carpathians: An overview. In: Grečula, M., Hovorka, D. & Putiš, M.: Geological Evolution of the Western Carpathians. Bratislava, *Miner. Slov. – Monograph.*, 1 – 24.
- PLAŠIENKA, D., HAVRILA, M., MICHALÍK, J., PUTIŠ, M. & REHÁKOVÁ, D., 1997b: Nappe structure of the western part of the Central Carpathians. In: Plašienka, D., Hók, J., Vozár, J. & Elečko, M. (eds.): 100th anniversary Dimitrij Andrusov; Alpine evolution of the Western Carpathians and related areas. International conference; abstracts and introductory articles to the excursion. Bratislava, *GS SR, Dionýz Štúr Publishers*, 139 – 161.
- PROKEŠOVÁ, R., 1994: Štruktúrna analýza krížňanského príkrovu v jeho prikoreňovej a superficiálnej pozícii. *Miner. Slov.*, 26, 347 – 354.
- PROKEŠOVÁ, R., PLAŠIENKA, D. & MILOVSKÝ, R., 2012: Structural pattern and emplacement mechanisms of the Krížna cover nappe (Central Western Carpathians). *Geol. Carpath.*, 63, 1, 13 – 32.
- RAMSAY, J. G., CASEY, M. & KLIFFIELD, R., 1983: Role of shear in development of the Helvetic fold-thrust belt of Switzerland. *Geology*, 11, 439 – 442.
- REHÁKOVÁ, D. & MICHALÍK, J., 1997: Evolution and distribution of calpionellids – the most characteristic constituents of Lower Cretaceous Tethyan microplankton. *Cret. Res.*, 18, 493 – 504.
- SENTPETERY, M. & HÓK, J., 2012: Geologická stavba tatrika a fatrika v oblasti medzi Belianskou a Vrátnou dolinou (Krivánska Fatra). *Acta Geol. Slov.*, 4, 1, 65 – 74.
- TOMAŠOVÝCH, A., 2004: Microfacies and depositional environment of an Upper Triassic intra-platform carbonate basin: The Fatric Unit of the West Carpathians (Slovakia). *Facies*, 50, 77 – 105.
- TYSZKA, J. & THIES, A., 2001: *Spiroplectinata*, key benthic foraminifer genus for palaeoceanographic reconstruction of the Albian Lower Saxony Basin. *Cret. Res.*, 174, 199 – 220.
- VASS, D., BEGAN, A., GROSS, P., KAHAN, Š., KRÝSTEK, I., KÖHLER, E., LEXA, J., NEMČOK, J., RUŽIČKA, M. & VAŠKOVSKÝ, I., 1988: Regionálne geologické členenie Západných Karpát a severných výbežkov Panónskej panvy na území ČSSR. Mapa 1 : 500 000. Bratislava, *Geol. Úst. D. Štúra*.

Vrásová deformácia fatrika – prípadová štúdia z profilu Banka (Považský Inovec, Slovensko)

Horninové sekvencie fatrika vystupujú v Považskom Inovci prevažne v strednej a západnej časti pohoria (Ivanička et al., 2007, obr. 1). V bojníanskom bloku horniny fatrika tvorí dominantne zliechovská jednotka. Výskyty v seleckom bloku sú plošne obmedzené na okraje pohoria okolo Beckova a Patrovca, kde ich buduje beckovská jednotka (Ivanička et al., 2011; Pelech et al., 2012). V hlohoveckom bloku sa prítomnosť fatrikových komplexov nepotvrdila.

Skúmaný zárez novobudovanej cesty v južnej časti katastra obce Banka (obr. 2), ktorý je hlavným predmetom tohto článku, vznikol v priebehu rokov 2013 – 2014. Rozsiahle defilé v sedimentárnej sekvencii fatrika tvoria horniny triasového až spodnokriedového veku, z ktorých dominujú horniny osnického súvrstvia (obr. 3). Zárez cesty s odkrytými horninami fatrika je dlhý asi 180 m, má generálne južnú expozíciu a v.-z. priebeh. Nápadná vrásová deformácia hornín na lokalite je kombinovaná s mladším zlomovým porušením. Výrazná je tektonická redukcia viacerých členov, ako aj fakt, že väčšina sedimentárnych kontaktov je tektonizovaná. V dôsledku zvrásnenia na lokalite dominuje východný aj západný sklon vrstvomitosti (obr. 4). Vrásová deformácia je dôsledkom ohybového sklzu, častého vo vrstvomitých telesách, čo dokumentujú tektonické zrkadlá na zvrásnených medzivrstvomitých plochách. Prevládajú asymetrické mezovrásy so sklonom osovej roviny na východ a vergenciou na západ (obr. 5). Orientácia vrás je generálne v smere S – J, s lokálnymi

unduláciami (obr. 4b). Priečne prevrásnenie bolo pozorované v zanedbateľnej miere. V bridliciach párnického súvrstvia sme pozorovali aj kliváž sklonenú na východ, ktorá zdôrazňuje dominantný smer tektonického transportu (obr. 5d). Západovergentné štruktúry zodpovedajú paleoalpínskej deformačnej fáze veku spodná („stredná“) až vrchná krieda.

Skúmaná fatriková sekvencia je okrem západovergentných vrás a násunov postihnutá aj spätnými násunmi a vrásami s východnou vergenciou. Markantné, no menej početné ako západovergentné, sú spätné, východovergentné vrásy. Predstavujú ich prevažne pasívne ohybové vrásy, ktoré buď ohýbajú pôvodné západovergentné vrásy, alebo vzpriamené vrásové osi pôvodne neutrálnych vrás (obr. 2, 35 – 37 m). Niektoré zdanlivo východovergentné vrásy sú v skutočnosti iba Z-vrásy väčších komplexných vrás (obr. 6b). Aj lokálne pozorované S/C' pásy indikujú tektonický transport na východ. Spätné prešmyky modifikujú pôvodnú stavbu a nezriedka oddeľujú rigidné bloky so štruktúrnou paragenézou a západnou vergenciou (obr. 6a). Sukcesia štruktúr naznačuje, že spätné prešmyky sú mladšia naložená deformačná fáza, pravdepodobne oligocénneho až spodnomiocénneho veku. Zdokumentovaná je aj prítomnosť viacerých kenozoických zlomov vrátane kvartérnych.

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